

MediVQA: Medical Visual Question Answering using VisualBERT

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ABSTRACT:

Medical Visual Question Answering (VQA) aims to enhance automated medical image interpretation by enabling AI systems to generate accurate responses to clinical queries. This research focuses on advancing Medical VQA, with a particular emphasis on interpreting medical images to support diagnostic and decision-making processes. Using VQA-Med-2019, ImageCLEFmed_MEDVQA and SLAKE 1.0 datasets, we developed a specialized system tailored to the unique demands of medical VQA tasks. Our approach combines textual feature extraction via the BERT model with visual feature extraction using ResNet-101. These multimodal features are integrated and processed through the MLP-integrated VisualBERT model, optimized for classification tasks. The proposed system demonstrates robust performance in generating accurate answers to complex medical queries, showcasing its potential to enhance medical diagnostics, improve clinical workflows, and ultimately contribute to better patient care outcomes.

Keywords: BERT, CNNs, ImageCLEFmed_MEDVQA, SLAKE 1.0, VisualBERT, VQA and VQA-Med-2019.

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INTRODUCTION

Recent advancements in Artificial Intelligence (AI) have transformed various fields, ranging from healthcare and finance to autonomous systems and natural language processing [1]. In healthcare, AI-powered systems have revolutionized diagnostics, predictive analysis, and treatment plans enhancing clinical efficiency. AI have also transformed the way machines interact with visual data, leading to significant progress in Visual Question Answering (VQA). Traditional VQA systems are designed to generate textual answers based on general-purpose images. However, when applied to specialized domains like medical imaging, these systems encounter unique challenges. It requires precise interpretation of complex visual patterns, coupled with domain-specific knowledge, to assist in answering clinically relevant queries. [2,3]

The complexity of VQA lies in the need to understand subtle variations in visual features and integrate specialized knowledge for answering queries that span a wide range of diagnostic contexts. Tasks such as identifying the type of abnormalities, understanding the feature of the medical image, or confirming potential diagnoses demand not only advanced visual recognition capabilities but also robust NLP. Despite growing interest, medical VQA remains underexplored due to limited annotated

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datasets, variability across imaging modalities, and the inherent difficulty of integrating textual and visual data meaningfully.

In this work, we developed a specialized MediVQA system that fuses textual and visual features for effective question-answering in clinical scenarios. We employ BERT [4] for extracting contextualized text features and CNNs for capturing visual features from medical images, integrating these multimodal representations within an MLP-enhanced VisualBERT framework optimized for classification tasks. Our system is trained and evaluated on diverse medical VQA datasets, demonstrating its capability to answer complex medical queries accurately. The results underline its potential to reduce diagnostic errors, enhance clinical workflows, and improve patient outcomes. Specialized datasets like VQA-MED2019 [5] and SLAKE [6] have been instrumental in driving progress, providing tailored resources for training models on radiology and medical imaging. The use of advanced visual feature extractors, such as ResNet [7], AlexNet [8], and VGG [9], along with Transformer models [10] like VisualBERT [11], has facilitated the development of systems that effectively bridge the gap between visual and textual data. A notable approach in this domain is the MLP-integrated VisualBERT, which improves token interactions using cross-token and cross-channel modules, enhancing the model's performance in medical image analysis, where understanding spatial relationships, anatomical structures, and disease patterns is vital.

Figure 1. Overview of the medical VQA

LITERATURE REVIEW

The domain of Visual Question Answering (VQA) represents a challenging intersection of computer vision and natural language processing, requiring systems to understand and reason over both visual and textual inputs. Early efforts in VQA primarily employed convolutional neural networks (CNNs) to extract visual features and recurrent neural networks (RNNs) [12], such as Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) [13] models, to encode textual questions [14]. These models relied on attention mechanisms to align relevant image regions with textual components, which proved effective in datasets like VQA 1.0 and 2.0 [15]. However, such architectures often suffered from limited cross-modal interaction, as they treated vision and language processing as sequential and somewhat independent tasks.

The introduction of transformer-based architectures has significantly enhanced VQA by enabling joint processing of visual and textual modalities. Transformer models, such as VisualBERT [11], unified these modalities within a single framework, leveraging self-attention mechanisms to model interactions between image regions and question tokens. This approach demonstrated superior performance, particularly in handling complex reasoning queries, as evidenced by evaluations on general-purpose datasets like CLEVR [16] and VQA 2.0. Transformers not only improved answer

accuracy but also provided better interpretability by explicitly highlighting relationships between text and image elements.

The success of VQA in general-purpose domains paved the way for its application in medical settings, where the tasks are inherently more complex and domain-specific. Medical Visual Question Answering (MediVQA) builds upon these foundations but faces unique challenges, including the scarcity of annotated datasets, the need for domain expertise, and the critical nature of interpretability in clinical applications. Early MediVQA systems adapted CNN-LSTM pipelines, initially successful in general VQA, to medical datasets such as VQA-RAD [17]. These methods demonstrated the feasibility of answering medical queries related to radiology images but lacked the nuanced understanding required for complex reasoning tasks.

The advent of transformers revolutionized MediVQA by enabling models to jointly learn from visual and textual data within a single framework. VisualBERT [11] and similar transformer-based models were fine-tuned on medical datasets such as VQA-Med [5] and SLAKE, significantly improving performance on tasks ranging from disease diagnosis to visual grounding. For instance, SLAKE introduced semantically labeled datasets that demanded models not only to answer questions but also to identify specific regions in medical images, a capability where transformers excelled.

Furthermore, recent efforts emphasize integrating domain knowledge to enhance reasoning capabilities. Knowledge-augmented transformers, such as those incorporating clinical knowledge graphs, further improved the interpretability and accuracy of responses [18]. By aligning textual queries with medically relevant image regions, these systems addressed critical challenges in understanding complex diagnostic and reasoning-based queries. These advancements highlight the transformative impact of transformer architectures in MediVQA, enabling systems to better support clinical decision-making and improve healthcare delivery.

DATASET

For this study, we utilized three prominent medical VQA datasets — VQA-Med-2019, ImageCLEFmed_MEDVQA and SLAKE 1.0 — each offering unique characteristics and challenges that contribute to the robustness and generalizability of our proposed model. These datasets collectively cover a wide range of medical imaging modalities, question types, and clinical contexts, providing a comprehensive foundation for developing a specialized medical VQA system.

VQA Med 2019 Dataset

MED-VQA 2019 dataset is composed of radiology images categorized into four main groups: Modality, Plane, Organ System, and Abnormality. This dataset serves as the primary foundation for our model development. The dataset encompasses a variety of questions related to organs, planes and so on. These questions represent the diverse range of queries for which answers were generated within this dataset.

For the VQA-Med-2019 dataset, preprocessing involves converting image files from .jpg format to .png and filtering the question-answer pairs to retain only those that align with a predefined set of answer classes. Each image is associated with a corresponding text file, named "imagename_QA.txt," containing the relevant question-answer pairs. The dataset is subsequently divided into training, validation, and testing subsets, with images and corresponding question-answer text files placed in separate folders. Table 1 shows the train, validation and testing set distribution of VQA Med 2019 dataset after preprocessing.

Table 1. VQA-Med-2019 Dataset after Preprocessing

Datatype	Total Images	Total Q/A pairs
Training	3,200	9,710
Validation	500	1,523
Testing	375	375

ImageCLEFmed_MEDVQA

The ImageCLEFmed_MEDVQA dataset [19] consists of 2,684 files, encompassing medical images, corresponding masks, and metadata. This dataset is specifically designed for the Gastrointestinal (GI) Task and includes various imaging modalities such as CT scans, ultrasounds, and X-rays. It aims to advance research in medical image analysis by addressing three key sub-tasks: Visual Question Answering (VQA), Visual Question Generation (VQG), and Visual Location Question Answering (VLQA).

For the preprocessing of ImageCLEFmed_MEDVQA dataset, image files are renamed to .png format, and a corresponding text file for each image is created, containing the relevant question-answer pairs. The dataset is then split into training and testing subsets using a 75-25% random selection with a fixed seed. Table 2 shows ImageCLEFmed_MEDVQA dataset description after preprocessing. There are unique 58 answers in the dataset.

Table 2. ImageCLEFmed_MEDVQA Dataset after Preprocessing

Datatype	Total Images	Total Q/A pairs
Training	1,500	27,503
Validation	500	9,180

SLAKE 1.0 Dataset

The SLAKE (Semantically Labeled Knowledge Enhanced Dataset) dataset is annotated by experienced physicians for Medical Visual Question Answering tasks. The dataset is available in both English and Chinese languages, aiming to enhance accessibility for a broader range of researchers. With its comprehensive annotations and multi-language support, the SLAKE dataset serves as a valuable resource in the field of Medical Visual Question Answering, facilitating advancements in medical image understanding and algorithm development.

SLAKE 1.0 dataset undergoes a preprocessing procedure where question-answer pairs are filtered to retain those with answers that appear more than 50 times. Table 3 shows SLAKE 1.0 dataset description used to evaluate MLPintegratedVisualBERT model.

Table 3. SLAKE 1.0 Dataset after Preprocessing

Datatype	Total Images	Total Q/A pairs
Training	481	3,969
Validation	161	1,273

PROPOSED FRAMEWORK

The proposed system for medical visual question answering (VQA) leverages multi-modal learning by integrating visual and textual feature representations using a novel MLP-integrated VisualBERT architecture. The system comprises feature extraction, multi-modal fusion, and sentence-level answer generation. In the feature extraction stage, visual features are obtained using a pre-trained Convolutional Neural Network (CNN), which provides rich image-level embeddings. Textual features are extracted by tokenizing questions with a domain-specific BERT tokenizer, enhancing contextual understanding of medical terminology. This combined approach ensures precise alignment of both modalities for downstream processing. The overall process is depicted in Figure 2.

The MLP-integrated VisualBERT model (Figure 3) builds upon the VisualBERTResMLP architecture [20] by incorporating cross-token and cross-channel interactions, enabling enhanced multi-modal fusion. The architecture includes embedding layers, self-attention modules, and specialized MLPResBlock (Figure 4a) components to improve feature integration. The MLPResBlock comprises cross-channel and cross-token (Figure 4b) mechanisms. The cross-channel module processes intra-token features using linear transformations, activation functions, and layer normalization to enrich individual token representations. The cross-token module transposes feature matrices to enable

inter-token information exchange, promoting deeper integration of visual and textual embeddings. These modules are linked via skip connections, ensuring efficient gradient flow and stable training. The sequential application of cross-channel and cross-token operations enhances the learning of complex inter-modal dependencies.

Figure 2. Block Diagram of the System

Figure 3. Block Diagram MLPintegratedVisualBERT Model

This process can be formalized by the following equations:

$$MLP = B(\text{GeLU}(A(X))) \quad (1)$$

$$X_{CC1} = \text{Norm}(X_{SA} + MLP(X_{SA})) \quad (2)$$

$$X_{CT} = \text{Norm}((D(X_{CC1}^T))^T) \quad (3)$$

$$X_{CC2} = \text{Norm}(X_{CC1} + MLP(X_{CT})) \quad (4)$$

Here, X_{CC1} and X_{CC2} denote the first and second cross-channel outputs, respectively, while X_{CT} represents the cross-token output.

MLPResBlock captures fine-grained relationships between visual and textual elements, enhancing model expressiveness and performance. The integration of feature extraction, multi-modal fusion, and downstream task handling results in a cohesive system capable of addressing complex vision and language challenges. The pooler, positioned after the MLP-integrated VisualBERT, distills its output into a compact representation optimized for classification while the prediction layer, implemented as a linear transformation with learned weights, maps the representation from the pooler to the target output space from where we get the classified answer. The question and the classified answer representations are then fed into the Gemini API, which generates sentence-level answers. For medical visual question answering, it predicts the most relevant answer by computing a probability distribution over potential responses, applying a softmax function for classification tasks. This design ensures that the system effectively combines visual and textual cues to produce accurate and context-sensitive answers.

Figure 4. Block Diagram of (a) MLPResBlock (b) Cross-Token

EXPERIMENTS

System Integration and Training

The model was trained with a well-defined architecture, utilizing the Adam optimization algorithm to minimize the cross-entropy loss function. Training used a batch size of 64, a dropout rate of 0.1, and a patch size of 5 in the visual feature extractor. The learning rate started at 0.00001, with a learning rate decay of 20% applied if validation accuracy did not improve over five consecutive epochs. Early stopping was employed to prevent overfitting. Hyperparameters included an embedding dimension of 300, 8 attention heads, a hidden layer size of 1024, 6 encoder layers, and a maximum question length of 25. The model was trained on an RTX 3070 Laptop GPU.

Training with Different CNN Architecture

Additionally, we conducted experiments by training the model using various CNNs for visual feature extraction, aiming to assess their effectiveness in capturing meaningful features from medical images. The choice of diverse CNN architectures allowed us to investigate their individual contributions to the model's performance in the context of medical image understanding, enabling a deeper analysis of their ability to extract relevant visual features for the task at hand.

Comparison with Baseline Models

For comparison, we also trained the baseline models, VisualBERT and VisualBERTResMLP, on VQA-Med-2019, SLAKE 1.0, and ImageCLEFmed_MEDVQA datasets to validate the effectiveness of our model. This comparison allowed us to assess the improvements introduced by the integration of the MLP mechanism and its impact on the model's performance in the medical visual question answering task.

RESULT AND ANALYSIS

To enhance the performance of medical Visual Question Answering (VQA), we propose the MLPintegratedVisualBERT model, which incorporates MLP-based feature transformation within the VisualBERT framework. This integration aims to improve the fusion of textual and visual information,

enabling more effective reasoning over medical images. Unlike standard VisualBERT, which relies on transformer-based attention alone, MLP layers allow additional nonlinear transformations, capturing high-level interactions between textual and visual features more effectively. These improvements contribute to a more robust and accurate VQA system, ultimately enhancing its ability to generate precise and contextually relevant answers.

The experiments evaluating the feature extraction capabilities of various CNN models, including different ResNet variants, AlexNet, and VGGNet (Table 4), within the MLPintegratedVisualBERT framework provide valuable insights into their performance on the VQA-MED 2019 dataset. Among the tested models, ResNet-101 achieved the highest accuracy (76.27%), while ResNet-18 recorded the lowest (72.00%), suggesting that increased depth can enhance feature extraction, though not always linearly. However, ResNet-152 (73.33%), despite being deeper than ResNet-101, did not show further improvements, suggesting diminishing returns and potential overfitting in very deep networks. AlexNet (75.73%) and VGG-16 (74.67%) exhibited comparable performance to ResNet-101, highlighting that moderate-depth architectures can effectively balance accuracy and computational efficiency. These results emphasize that while deeper networks often perform better, choosing the deepest network may not always be the best option. Optimal feature extraction depends on dataset complexity, network architecture, and computational constraints, making model selection a critical factor in medical VQA systems where visual reasoning plays a key role. Therefore, these findings highlight the importance of conducting comparative evaluations and selecting feature extractors based on their suitability for the specific task at hand.

Table 4. Accuracy Scores for different Features extractors.

Model	Accuracy (%)
ResNet-18	72.00
ResNet-152	73.33
ResNet-101	76.27
VGG-16	74.67
AlexNet	75.73

The experimental results (Table 5) demonstrate the superior performance of the proposed MLPintegratedVisualBERT model compared to the baseline models, VisualBERT and VisualBERTResMLP, across all three datasets: VQA-Med-2019, SLAKE 1.0, and ImageCLEFmed_MEDVQA. Specifically, MLPintegratedVisualBERT achieved the highest testing accuracy of 76.27% on VQA-Med-2019, representing an improvement of 2.14% over VisualBERT and 1.07% over VisualBERTResMLP. On SLAKE 1.0, the model achieved comparative performance, with an accuracy of 90.18% compared to 90.10% for VisualBERT. Similarly, for ImageCLEFmed_MEDVQA, the model attained an accuracy of 91.05%, slightly surpassing VisualBERTResMLP and VisualBERT. These findings highlight the effectiveness of integrating MLP components into the VisualBERT architecture, as this enhancement appears to improve the model's ability to capture and utilize complex visual-linguistic relationships. Although VisualBERTResMLP showed some improvements over VisualBERT, the gains were not consistent, suggesting that the full integration of MLP within VisualBERT yields more significant benefits. Furthermore, the use of the Gemini API for sentence-level answer generation enabled the production of comprehensible and contextually understandable outputs, aligning well with the practical requirements of medical VQA applications.

These results highlight the effectiveness of a structured integration of MLP layers and Cross-Channel operations within the VisualBERT framework. While VisualBERTResMLP also incorporates MLP components, a key distinction lies in the Cross-Channel processing. MLPintegratedVisualBERT applies Cross-Channel operations both before and after transposition, whereas VisualBERTResMLP applies it only after transposition. This dual-stage processing enhances feature transformation and fusion, capturing essential interactions from raw inputs and later refining the fused representation. The structured combination of self-attention, normalization, skip connections, and cross-token

interactions further optimizes information flow, leading to superior reasoning capabilities and improved performance across datasets.

Table 5. Performance of Various Models on Different Datasets

Model	VQA-Med-2019 (%)	Slake 1.0 (%)	ImageCLEFmed MEDVQA (%)
VisualBERT	74.13	90.10	90.61
VisualBERTResMLP	75.20	89.47	90.95
MLPintegrated VisualBERT	76.27	90.18	91.05

CONCLUSION

In this study, we proposed MLPintegratedVisualBERT, a novel extension of the VisualBERT architecture that incorporates MLP components to enhance visual-linguistic feature extraction. The model was evaluated on three medical VQA datasets: VQA-Med-2019, SLAKE 1.0, and ImageCLEFmed_MEDVQA, consistently outperforming baseline models in terms of testing accuracy demonstrating its effectiveness in handling complex visual-linguistic tasks. These improvements highlight the significance of integrating MLP components into the VisualBERT framework for better feature representation and utilization. Additionally, the integration of the Gemini API enabled the generation of comprehensible and contextually relevant sentence-level answers, enhancing the practical applicability of the system for real-world medical VQA tasks. While the proposed model shows significant advancements, especially on complex datasets, the performance gains for simpler datasets, such as SLAKE 1.0 and ImageCLEFmed_MEDVQA, were relatively modest. This study primarily focused on classification, and further exploration of the interplay between classification and natural language generation could enhance the end-to-end system. In the future, pretraining can be conducted using diverse medical image-caption datasets, such as the ROCO [21] dataset, to enhance the model's learning capability and improve its accuracy.

CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

No conflict of interest.

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